

PERCEIVED SERVANT LEADERSHIP AND EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION: A PARALLEL MEDIATION MODEL WITH REFERENCE TO HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR OF KARACHI

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This study is based on multiple knowledge gaps and contextual gaps that need to be addressed for a better understanding of servant leadership in the higher education sector. However, for a better understanding and academic contribution, this study has been conducted with reference to the higher education section of Pakistan to make readers understand the implications of servant leadership in Pakistan.

Research Gap: Recent studies discuss the relationship between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction. Especially with the mediation of job-related variables, there is a severe lacking of research that are associated with servant leadership. This gap is more prominent with respect to Asian Developing Markets. Therefore, this study has been conducted with reference to Pakistan.

Methodology: This study is one of the correlational designs that are based upon primary data collected from the faculty of management sciences operating in private higher education institutes & universities of Karachi. The data has been collected through quota sampling, and the sample size for the study is 300 respondents.

Findings: The findings of this study affirm the importance of servant leadership in the higher education sector of Karachi. The study also indicated that a model developed through citing various knowledge and contextual gaps is found to be legitimate. However, one of the minor claims of the study has not been proved due to difference in the implications of servant leadership for different industries.

Practical Implications: Hence, through this study, policymakers may develop efficient means to highlight the significance of servant leadership in the higher education sector of Karachi.

Significance of the study: This is one of the most significant studies that is beneficial for the academic and pragmatic world and has the tendency to improve understanding, flourish thorough research work, and assist in policy making related to leadership in higher education institutions.

JEL Classification: M1, M12, M14, J80, L84 & I2

1.0) Background

Research highlighted that most of the leadership models are observed under an organizational setting and can only be assessed on the basis of behavior of the supervisor. However, servant leadership is different in that it actually stems from inside the person. Hence, it is appropriate to state that the values, beliefs, and thoughts of the servant leaders are the major reasons behind their motivation and behavior (Ingram, 2016). The term “Servant Leader” was initially proposed in the year 1977, and the role of a servant leader is to increase the skills of subordinates and also to remove hindrances from the path of the follower. According to researchers, servant leaders understand that the followers are humans who have different type of needs and these needs may be addressed by supervisors through making their subordinates motivated in an adequate manner (Sepahvand et al., 2015).

According to research, servant leadership is not a new concept, as it is practiced all over the globe without restriction of culture or economy, etc. The concept of servant leadership is based upon the protection and persuasion of subordinate interest over the interest of the supervisor (Guillaume et al., 2013)

1.1) Introduction

Job satisfaction of employees served as the backbone of productivity. The same is the case of academia, where job satisfaction serves as the backbone of academic work. Hence, brain drain in higher education is a critical issue that causes a severe impact on the performance of higher educational institutions. On the other side, satisfied staff plays a critical role in multiple domains, and their satisfaction is found to be fruitful in developing organizational reputation through the learning and performance of students. According to research, multiple factors are found to be important in shaping job satisfaction of academic staff, among them one is leadership, which is perceived as one of the most important factors that cause job satisfaction. Research advocates for the importance of leadership in shaping employee job satisfaction and productivity in higher education. Similar is

valid for the importance of servant leadership has the highest score over job satisfaction. Hence, servant leadership is perceived as one of the most important forms of leadership to influence employee attitude and behavior. Therefore, an increase in interest towards the research work related with servant leadership is on the higher side, especially in higher education. Hence, research work that may substantiate the understanding related to servant leadership in academia is carried out in a diverse range of countries, e.g., America, Ethiopia, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Pakistan, and Palestine etc (Dami et al., 2022).

1.2) Statement of Problem

According to research, very few studies have determined the relationship between servant leadership in academia. Studies that relate servant leadership with employee job satisfaction require attention and focus in order to increase research inventory in the required area. Moreover, most of the studies related with servant leadership in the context of higher education haven't used job-related behavior as the mediators to test job satisfaction. Hence, the use of job-related variables to check the mediating relationship would substantiate the research and its outcomes (Dami et al., 2022). Especially, the importance of this exploration is substantial for the academic world, where the role of servant leadership is substantial for improvement in satisfaction of faculty (Floyd, 2023). However, there is still required to cover the un-known about the impact of servant leadership on the personalities and job satisfaction faculty operating in the higher education sector (Guillaume et al., 2013). Similar is the indication of Amin et al (2019) who mentioned that future research may explore the impact of servant leadership on the motivational factors of faculty.

1.3) Theoretical Underpinning

The leader-member exchange (LMX) theory developed by Liden et al (1997) and the major contribution of this theory is the contribution of leadership behavior in supervisor-employee relationship. In-depth analysis of the leader-

member exchange theory revealed that nourishment of the full potential of the employee is based upon the relationship between the leader & member. Hence, in relation with the leader-member exchange theory, the role of servant leadership is to boost employee morale to facilitate employee growth and employee development (Dami et al., 2022). The LMX Theory is a well-structured and developed theory that has been tested in multiple industries and has been found to be positive in highlighting the relationship of the servant leader and the member. According to research, the LMX theory has also been tested in the higher education sector and reflects positively on the job satisfaction of subordinates (El-Bayaa et al., 2023). Studies using LMX as the base of the study also highlighted that the use of LMX has a significant impact on employee engagement (Akdol & Arikboga, 2017)

1.4) Research Model

Sokoll (2014) indicated that servant leadership is used to create an association between supervisor and subordinate through motivation and developing employees. Hence, the immediate outcome of servant leadership is employee commitment to the supervisor. On the other hand, Rivkin et al (2014) indicated that there is also a direct and positive impact of servant leadership on the general health of employees. However, one of the latest studies by Henry and Uzoechi (2025) highlighted that there is a direct association between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction. However, most of the studies, e.g., Dami et al (2022), highlight an indirect association between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction. Similar points are also posited by Rivkin et al (2014) and Sokoll (2014) that immediate outcomes of servant leadership are not the job satisfaction of employees. Hence, the model of this study uses job satisfaction as the only outcome variable of servant leadership in order to test the mediating variables highlighted by Sokoll (2014) and Rivkin et al (2014) in order to assess the impact of servant leadership through a parallel mediation model.

1.5) Significance & Scope of the Study

This study is one of the pervasive studies as the purpose of this study has multiple folds, one of which is to check the parallel mediation in the relationship of servant leadership in the higher education industry and employee's job satisfaction. According to research, staff retention is one of the most important elements to achieve sustainable competitive advantage in the higher education sector of Pakistan (Butt et al., 2020). Hence, higher education in Pakistan is the best possible sector to test the points and gaps posited by Dami et al (2022). Therefore, this study can be used by academicians and researchers for a better understanding and through research work. Hence, this study also has the potential to contribute to the practical learning of intrapreneurs from the higher education sector. Lastly, this study is based upon knowledge gaps and contextual gaps, and through fulfilling these gaps, this study also has the tendency to contribute to policy making related with the higher education sector for better employee wellbeing and job satisfaction.

2.0) Literature Review

Initial studies using Leader-Member Exchange theory highlighted that Servant Leadership is found to be directly correlated with trust, satisfaction and fairness in a positive manner (Van Dierendonck 2011). Hence, it is legitimate to believe that servant leaders are the true facilitators who will not only empower their subordinates but will also facilitate growth and development of their followers (Liden et al., 2015). Hence, in the light of these points servant leadership has a definite association with achievement of personal and organizational goals. Therefore, studying servant leadership is not only significant for the academic world but also provides some relevant and important implications for different industries. Therefore servant leadership through complying with ethical, spiritual and value-laden philosophies is very important for public limited and private limited organization (Alahbabi et al., 2021). On the other hand, a leader's decision and actions also has the tendency to affect organizational

culture, employee personality but also employee health (Guillaume et al., 2013). Therefore, the upcoming literature will present a detailed review of the relationship of servant leadership with employee health and job-related behavior to check the indirect effect of servant leadership over employee job satisfaction.

2.1) Servant Leadership & Commitment to Supervisor:

Becker et al (1996) highlighted that servant leadership is the form of leadership that aims to develop long-term relationships with employees. Hence, a supervisor who exhibits the characteristics of servant leadership will try to develop employees and flourish their careers in the long run. Hence, employees are also found to be inclined towards supervisors that are ranked higher in attributes of servant leadership. Similar research has also been proved through statistical analysis where 22.4% of the variance in employee commitment towards the supervisor has been explained by servant leadership (Sokoll, 2014). Hence, it is appropriate to quote servant leadership resulting in affective and normative commitment towards the supervisor (Godbersen et al., 2024) and use of gender as the control variable between the relationship of supervisor and subordinate may result in further clarification of results (Sokoll, 2014). Similar points are valid for the education sector where servant leadership has the tendency to foster loyalty among subordinates (Demir, 2022)

H_{1A}: There is a relationship between servant leadership and commitment to supervisor

2.2) Servant Leadership & Improvement in Employee Health

Rivkin et al (2014) postulated that there is a direct relationship between servant leadership and betterment of physiological health of individuals. According to research servant leadership is negatively related with emotional exhaustion (Rivkin & Schmidt, 2016). Similarly indicated by Winston (2022) that servant leadership produced positive impact over employee general wellbeing due to effective work environment and organizational support. Dilley

et al (2025) also highlighted the direct association between servant leadership and employee health. Hence, tested servant leadership as the moderator between stress and employee health and findings of the study revealed that servant leadership has the ability to decrease and improve employee health conditions through removal of stress.

H_{2A}: There is a relationship between servant leadership and General Improvement in employee Health

2.3) Commitment to Supervisor & Employee Job Satisfaction

Initial Studies e.g., Backer et al (1996) highlighted that employee commitment is a multi-dimensional construct. However, dimensions of employee commitment are not equally correlated with employee performance. Hence, conceptualization of the construct was required which revealed that commitment to the supervisor is strongly related to employee performance in comparison to the employee commitment towards the organization (Sokoll, 2014). These points are also supported by Prayitno and Fikry (2025) that employees who are supported by their supervisor have higher levels of job satisfaction. Especially important is emotional support that resulted in an increase of job satisfaction (Ngoc et al., 2024) that ultimately increased subordinates' commitment towards the supervisor (Redebe & Dhurup, 2017).

H_{3A}: There is a relationship between commitment to supervisor and employee job satisfaction

2.3) Improvement in Employee Health & Employee Job Satisfaction

Chang (2024) highlighted that employees with good health are more motivated than those who do not possess the required level of health. Hence, the motivated employees are not only regular and punctual to work but also found to be more satisfied. Similar is valid for Asia where companies are required to consult their employees regularly in order to improve work conditions and organizational culture (Wu, 2024) However, gender composition may result in different results as indicated by Cass et al (2003)

for organizations in Hong Kong. Thus, it is appropriate to quote Chang (2024) who highlighted the success of those organizations who gain success through taking holistic initiatives to improve mental and physical health of employees. According to the study, employees with better physiological health are not only punctual at work but also have more job satisfaction that will ultimately produce better results for the organization. Hence, organizations are also required to develop optimal strategies to improve employee wellbeing through sound employee development process, promoting work-life balance and attractive compensation structure (Sri et al., 2024)

H₄A: There is a relationship between improvement in employee health and employee job satisfaction

2.4) Servant Leadership, Commitment to Supervisor & Employee Job Satisfaction

Servant Leadership addresses the employee job satisfaction and the relationships is valid across multiple sectors (Uktutias et al., 2022 & Vrcelj et al., 2024) through addressing various employee needs and develop sense of purpose and belongingness towards the leader (Naa et al., 2024). Sokoll (2013) highlighted trust and respect as the major reason due to which servant leadership pushes commitment towards the supervisor. Study further mentioned that the relationship between servant leadership and commitment of employee towards supervisor is also critical diminishing employee turnover intention.

H₅A: Commitment to supervisor mediates between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction

2.5) Servant Leadership, Improvement in Employee Health & Employee Job Satisfaction

Alahbabi et al (2021) highlighted employee happiness as one of the important mediators between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction. Mitterer (2017) also highlighted that servant leadership creates a positive impact over the physiological conditions of the subordinate that ultimately increase employee job satisfaction.

Zada et al (2022) also indicated that servant leadership reduces physiological distress which makes employees more satisfied with their job.

H₅A: Improvement in employee health mediates between servant leadership and employee job satisfaction

3.0) Research Methodology

Research Methodology is an essential part of the research, and its purpose is to make readers understand why researchers prefer different methodological elements over the other in the formulation of the study (Kothari, 2004). Hence, multiple references, e.g., Saunders et al (2007); Saunders et al (2015), and Sekaran and Bougie (2016) are used by researchers all over the globe to develop effective and sound research methodologies. However, Sekaran and Bougie (2016) highlighted that it is better to divide research methodology into multiple layers, i.e., research design, sampling design, and research instrument. Division will clarify the use of assumptions, postulates, and references used by researchers that ultimately resulted in the creation of a better impact over the understanding of the readers.

3.1) Research Design:

The purpose of this research is correlational, as indicated by Sekaran and Bougie (2016), as it used variables from multiple studies and different research models to develop a workable research model. Hence, the philosophy related to this study is epistemology, which is the philosophy of knowledge (Saunders et al., 2007).

However, considering the framework of research onion provided by Saunders et al (2015) it is required to use philosophical stance to make a connection between research philosophy and research approach. Hence, this study uses post-positivism through considering Bisel and Adame (2017) which highlighted post-positivist epistemology as a socially constructed phenomenon that permits a more flexible approach for data collection and analysis. The approach used for the compilation of this study is deductive reasoning, methodological choice incorporated is mono-method, the research

strategy is survey, and the time horizon is cross-sectional. All these methodological parameters were highlighted by Saunders et al (2007) and Saunders et al (2015), and the selection of these parameters is legitimate as this study is based on research gaps highlighted by previous researchers, compiled in a single instant of time through primary data.

3.2) Sampling Design:

The sampling plan used in this study coincides with the working of Dooley et al (2020) and Zada et al (2022) to collect data through using a non-

probability sampling technique, and the sampling method was quota sampling. Amin et al (2019) conducted a study on servant leadership in the Higher education Sector of Karachi, also preferred non-probability sampling. Hence, most of the studies use non-probability sampling for data collection, except studies like Alahbabi et al (2023) and Sokoll (2013), who conducted their studies with reference to one particular company. However, conducting the study with reference to one particular company may decrease the rigor of the study.

Table 3.1 Description of Participants

Gender	
Males	39%
Females	61%
Age	
Up to 30 Years	13%
31-40 Years	37%
41-50	30%
51-60 Years	20%
Experience	
1-5 Years	21%
6-10 Years	24%
11-15 Years	30%
16-20 Years	19%
21-25 Years	06%

Thus, quota sampling has been used in order to collect data from all the permanent faculty members of Higher Education Institutes of Karachi. A similar sampling method was used by Anshori et al (2023) and Hawladar and Rahman (2021) to collect data from the educational and private banking sectors.

Hence, this study collected the sample for this study from employees of the higher educational sector with permanent employee status in the faculty of management sciences or business. The sample size for the study was 300 respondents who are working as permanent faculty in private sector universities and the Higher Educational Institute of Karachi. Initially, 400 questionnaires were circulated; however, due to issues of inadequate responses and missing data, this study has been compiled with a 75% response rate.

3.3) Research Instrument:

The Research Instrument used in this study is a structured, closed-ended questionnaire. The tool is found to be used in multiple studies related with servant leadership and employee job satisfaction, e.g., Alahbabi et al (2023), and also used by Dilley et al (2025), who use servant leadership as the moderating variable between stress and employee health. However, elements used in the study are not retrieved from only these studies that are also required to increase the reliability and validity of the instrument. However, the research instrument used in the study follows the same pattern used by Alahbabi et al (2023) and Dilley et al (2025) as it is also based upon a five-point Likert scale.

4.0) Statistical Testing & Analysis

Previous studies related with the topic of servant leadership, e.g., Alahbabi et al (2023) and Sokoll (2013) also uses structural equation modeling to assess the impact of servant leadership on employees. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is one of the most important statistical tools that are perceived to be better for statistical analysis in comparison to regression (Gunzeler, 2013). Use of SMART-PLS has the ability to make SEM more effective and rigorous for the assessment of causal and temporal relationships. Therefore, SMART-PLS has been preferred by statisticians

and researchers for efficient assessment of primary data (Wong, 2017). The basis of SMART-PLS are based on the outer (structural) model and inner (measurement) model (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). The outer model is used to check the relationship of observed elements with the relevant latent variables and the purpose of the inner model is to check the association between latent variables (Wong, 2013). Therefore, the use of software is significantly important for researchers and academicians for highlighting descriptive and inferential statistics associated with the research model (Ogwig & Lasisi, 2022)

Table 4.1 Construct Reliability and Convergent Validity

Variable	Outer Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Goldstein rho	Composite Reliability	AVE
Servant Leadership	0.883	0.888	0.943	0.920	0.742
	0.908				
	0.820				
	0.832				
General Improvement in Employee Health	0.868	0.899	0.900	0.930	0.768
	0.887				
	0.878				
	0.872				
Commitment to Supervisor	0.760	0.873	0.885	0.913	0.726
	0.911				
	0.903				
	0.826				
Employee 's Job Satisfaction	0.843	0.876	0.885	0.915	0.731
	0.890				
	0.896				
	0.786				

Table 4.1, along with Figure 1, is the purposive use of descriptive statistical tools that are highlighted by Ab Hmid et al (2017). Table 1 includes multiple elements to highlight descriptive statistics, e.g., Outer Loading, Cronbach's alpha & Goldstein rho for assessing construct reliability and Outer Loading, Composite reliability & Average Variance Extracted for Convergent Validity. The range of

values for outer loading ranges from 0 to 1 but according to research, it is better to select those indicators that yield outer loading values that are equal to or greater than 0.70. Therefore, according to Aftahnorhan (2013) it is optimal to delete any indicator with a value lower than 0.70 provided that the deletion is found significant for overall convergent validity.

Figure 4.1: Structural Model

Similar values are preferred for the validation of Cronbach's alpha & Goldstein rho (Ab Hamid et al., 2017). However, if the value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is found to be greater than 0.50, then researchers will not require any other element to proof convergent validity of the research model (Ab Hamid et al., 2017 & Adeleke et al., 2015). Hence, in light of the parameters and points mentioned, it is optimal to declare that table 4.1 is sufficiently fulfilling construct reliability, composite reliability, and convergent validity.

Table 4.2 is plotted to highlight discriminant validity via Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). According to Malik et al (2021), HTMT is one of

the most preferred tools for indicating discriminant validity in the research model. Similar propositions are also made by Hair et al (2019) to highlight the significance of HTMT in assessing discriminant validity. However, in order to assure discriminant validity through the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio, researchers must achieve benchmark values at the junction of intersecting variables, and no value greater than 0.85 would be substantial to highlight discriminant validity (Shaffer et al., 2016). Hence, in line with the protocols and points mentioned above, it is appropriate to believe that Table 4.2 sufficiently fulfills the requirement of discriminant validity.

Table 4.2: Discriminant Validity

	Commitment to Supervisor	Employee Job Satisfaction	General Improvement in Employee Health	Servant Leadership
Commitment to Supervisor				
Employee Job Satisfaction	0.764			
General Improvement in Employee Health	0.450	0.480		

Servant Leadership	0.444	0.136	0.204
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Table 4.3: Coefficient of Determination (Quality Criteria)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Commitment to Supervisor	0.586	0.581
Employee Job Satisfaction	0.492	0.489
General Improvement in Employee Health	0.536	0.534

Table 4.3 is used as the base of model fitness, and it is termed as coefficient of determination, that is based upon the percentage change in the values of the dependent variable due to a 1% change in the independent variable (Hahn, 1973). Sansui et al (2022) highlighted the benchmark values for effective assessment of result, e.g., values from 0.25 to 0.499 are termed as weak predictors, values from 0.50 to 0.74 predictors are termed as moderate, while 0.75 and above are termed as

strong predictors. Thus, it is appropriate to declare that Table 4.3 is sufficiently fulfills the requirement of the coefficient of determination as the values of R-Square for the entire range of outcome variables are greater than 0.25, that is the minimum acceptable criteria to bring change in the dependent variable. In fact, both of the mediators are affected moderately by a change in the independent while the outcome variable is also near the moderate change (effect).

Table 4.4: Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Commitment to Supervisor -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.609	0.607	0.058	10.520	0.000
General Improvement in Employee Health -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.179	0.188	0.054	3.302	0.001
Servant Leadership -> Commitment to Supervisor	0.400	0.396	0.083	4.823	0.000
Servant Leadership -> General Improvement in Employee Health	0.190	0.184	0.098	1.952	0.052

Table 4.4 is indicating the path coefficient that is used as a tool to understand the relationship between the variables used in the study. Thus, it is included in inferential statistical analysis related to statistical analysis. The purpose of using path-coefficient is to highlight all the valid paths and associations in the study, which is supplemented with SMART-PLS. However, there are pre-defined criteria that are used to understand the validity of the association between the variables. These measures are t-statistical values and p-values, and in order to affirm the association, there is a need to fulfill

both the criteria (Silaparsetti et al., 2017). The reference values are to evaluate t-statistical values and p-values is based upon the study of Hair et al (2017) and Hair et al (2019), who highlighted that t-statistical values must be equal to or greater than 1.97 and p-values must be lower than or equal to 0.05. Therefore, in the light of the parameters mentioned by Hair et al (2017) and Hair et al (2019), it is legitimate to declare the rejection of H₁O, H₃O & H₄O. However, due to a lower t-statistic value (1.952) and a higher p-value (0.052), it is required to highlight that there is no relationship between perceived servant

leadership and improvement in general employee health in the higher education sector. Therefore,

in accordance with the result, it is appropriate to accept H_2O

Figure 4.2: Measurement Model

Table 4.5 is the extended model of path-coefficient and used to indicate mediation analysis (Hair et al., 2019). Thus, the criteria provided by Silaparsetti et al (2017) are valid to judge the impact of mediation analysis. Hence, in line with Hair et al (2017) and Hair et al (2019), it is valid to assume that commitment to the

supervisor is the only valid mediator between perceived servant leadership and employee job satisfaction, and there is no mediation created by general improvement in employee health. Hence, in line with the results obtained from Table 4.5 researchers are required to reject H_3O and accept H_6O .

Table 4.5: Specific Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Servant Leadership -> Commitment to Supervisor -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.243	0.240	0.050	4.836	0.000
Servant Leadership -> General Improvement in Employee Health -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.034	0.033	0.020	1.727	0.085

Table 4.6: Total Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Commitment to Supervisor -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.609	0.607	0.058	10.520	0.000
General Improvement in Employee Health -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.179	0.188	0.054	3.302	0.001
Servant Leadership -> Commitment to Supervisor	0.400	0.396	0.083	4.823	0.000
Servant Leadership -> Employee Job Satisfaction	0.277	0.273	0.056	4.956	0.000
Servant Leadership -> General Improvement in Employee Health	0.190	0.184	0.098	1.952	0.052

Table 4.6 is reflecting total effects and the rubric to evaluate the results are the same as that are used to evaluate the results for Tables 4.4 and 4.5. The purpose of of total effect is to assess the impact of all the variables used in the study in order to understand the outcomes of the study in holistic manner (Ariyanto et al., 2024 & Saftari & Sinta, 2022). Hence, in line with Hair et al (2017) and Hair et al (2019), the impact of every variable is substantial except the impact of servant leadership on general improvement in employee health. However, the use of Table 4.4 and Table 4.6 are reflecting the positive association between general improvement in employee health and job performance, which means the variable (general improvement in

employee health), has the tendency to be used as the mediator.

5.0) Conclusion & Discussion

5.1) Conclusion

Conduct of detailed statistical testing through SMART-PLS revealed that the perceived servant leadership in the higher education sector of Pakistan is creating an indirect effect on employees' job satisfaction. However, for creating an indirect effect on employees' job satisfaction, supervisors are required to rely on the commitment of employees towards the supervisor. Hence, commitment to the supervisor is found to be an important mediator in this study. However, the other mediator, i.e., general improvement in employee health that has a direct

& positive association with employee's job satisfaction, does not have any mediating role. Hence, out of six major claims of the study, four claims are accepted, which justifies the model formation and relationship of both mediators with the dependent variable. However, as indicated previously, only one (Employee Commitment to Supervisor) causes mediating relationships

5.2) Discussion

Findings of this study were initially able to fill the knowledge gap and contextual gaps related with job-related factors and the higher education industry highlighted by Dami et al. (2022) and Guillaume et al. (2013), respectively. Therefore, in addition to the major claims, this study is also able to prove significance testing through fulfilling all the valid research gaps. However, fulfilling the research gaps is not the only point that adds to the significance of this study, as this study is also found to be in line with the leader-member exchange theory proposed by Liden et al. (1997) and also with Dami et al. (2022) to prove the impact and significance of servant leadership. Hence, the model developed through citing Dami et al. (2022), Henry and Uzoechi (2025), Sokoll (2014), and Rivkin et al. (2014) is also valid. Thus, declaring this study as one of the pervasive studies is legitimate. Therefore, all the postulates made by initial studies, e.g., Van Dierendonck (2011) and Liden et al. (2015) to legitimize that Servant Leadership is positively related with trust, satisfaction, and fairness in a positive manner. Therefore, servant leaders will not only empower their subordinates but will also facilitate the growth and development of their followers. Hence, there is no reason to deviate from Alahbabi et al. (2021), who claim that servant leadership is not only significant for the academic world but also provides some relevant and important implications for different industries. Reflecting vividly with respect to the variables used in this study, it is legitimate to quote that the study is found to be consistent with Becker et al. (1996) and Sokoll (2014) to legitimize the relationship between servant leadership and commitment to employees towards the supervisor

in the higher education sector of Karachi. However, the analysis found to be inconsistent with Dilley et al. (2025); Rivkin et al. (2014); Rivkin and Schmidt (2016), and Winston (2022), as there is no association found between Servant Leadership & Improvement in Employee Health. Therefore, it is legitimate to believe Lee et al. (2020), who indicated that servant leadership and its implications may vary across cultures. On the other hand, different methodological approaches used by studies also create limitations for applying leadership styles and their outcomes in a universal manner (Lawande & Venkatesh, 2025). However, selection of improvement as employee health through considering is not wrong, as the positive outcomes of the variable are found with employee job satisfaction. Therefore, the findings are in line with Chang (2024) and Wu (2024). However, the other mediator used in the study (i.e., commitment to supervisor) is found to be an efficient outcome variable for servant leadership. Hence, the finding is also consistent with Backer et al. (1996); Cass et al. (2003), Chang (2024); Sokoll (2014), and Sri et al. (2024). Similar is valid for the mediation caused by commitment to the supervisor, which is found true for this study for the higher education sector of Karachi (Naa et al., 2024 & Sokoll, 2014). However, the other mediation test in the study (general improvement in employee health) is not found to be true. Therefore, the findings of the study are inconsistent with Alahbabi et al. (2021), Mitterer (2017), and Zada et al. (2022).

5.3) Policy Implications

This study is useful to make readers understand the perceived outcomes of servant leadership in the higher education sector of Karachi. However, the findings are consistent with the impact of generic improvement in employee health. Therefore, policies are made to make subordinates develop measurable Key Performance Indicators to ensure the positive impact of servant leadership over employee commitment to the supervisor. This point has also been reflected by Amah (2018) and extended by Kumari et al. (2022) to develop proper measures to highlight the methods and means to

gauge the impact of servant leadership over employees.

5.4) Area for Future Research

Considering this study, future study can be conducted to explore the impact of perceived servant leadership in the government sector, Higher Educational Institute & Universities of Karachi. However, better studies are required to be conducted through controlling variables on the basis of different faculties e.g., Management Sciences, Social Sciences, Engineering Sciences, etc. Lastly, conducive studies may be conducted through applying control variables in addition to optimization of the research model through adding serial or parallel mediation for efficient and thorough theoretical contribution. Moreover, the findings of this study are not consistent with the impact of servant leadership over general improvement in employee health as indicated by Chang (2024) and Wu (2024). Similarly, the mediation of general improvement in employee health has also not been found to be true. Therefore, future study may test the results with respect to different genders in order to pursue the points mentioned by Cass et al (2003).

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